

TABLE S1. Information of specimens used in ITS-based phylogenetic analysis of Gomphales in Fig. S1. Taxa marked with “(T)” represent type specimens.

Taxa	Locality	Voucher	ITS GenBank No.	References
Ingroup				
<i>Clavariadelphus occidentalis</i>	USA	OSC114281	EU846242	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>C. pistillaris</i>	Canada	3894	KM248917	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>C. truncatus</i>	Canada	SMI278	HQ650728	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>Gautieria caudata</i>	USA	OSC19937	AY558750	Izzo et al. 2005
	USA	OSC41323	AF377057	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
<i>G. chilensis</i>	Chile	RH5818	AF377069	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
<i>G. cf. crispa</i>	USA	SRC627	DQ974732	Smith et al. 2007
<i>G. gautierioides</i>	USA	HS2634	AF377062	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
<i>G. graveolens</i>	Italy	1139	FN666413	Direct submission by Camele
	Italy	16988	JF908017	Direct submission by Frank; Osmundson et al. 2013
	Bulgaria	SOMF29672	MN044442	Nedeli et al. 2016
<i>G. monticola</i>	USA	SNF95	AF377105	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
	USA	SNF136	AF377079	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
	USA	SNF312	AF377078	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
	USA	SNF334	AF377087	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
	USA	SNF346	AF377101	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
	USA	OSC48844	AF377092	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
<i>G. morchelliformis</i>	Switzerland	HH2222	AF377066	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
	USA	T4547	AF377067	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
<i>G. othii</i>	USA	T7852	AF377072	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
	USA	T8371	AF377073	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
<i>G. parksiana</i>	USA	SNF236	AF377059	Bidartondo & Bruns 2002
<i>G. mianjin</i> (T)	China	HKAS126926	OQ282702	This study
<i>G. xinjiangensis</i> (T)	China	HMJAU6009	NR153450	Bau & Liu 2013
<i>Gloeocantharellus aculeatus</i>	Brazil	FLOR47977	KU884895	Song et al. 2019
<i>Gl. corneri</i>	Brazil	FLOR47978	KU884898	Song et al. 2019
<i>Gl. echinosporus</i>	Solomon Islands	CGE16041	KU884899	Song et al. 2019
<i>Gl. neoechinosporus</i> (T)	China	GDGM75321	NR166272	Song et al. 2019
<i>Gomphus clavatus</i>	Sweden	EL64/03(GB)	EU118628	Liu et al. 2022a
<i>Go. crassipes</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi79908	MH322660	Liu et al. 2022a

<i>Go. ludovicianuss</i> (T)	USA	TENN69161	NR169660	Liu et al. 2022a
<i>Go. matijun</i> (T)	China	HKAS122604	OL673002	Liu et al. 2022a
<i>Go. orientalis</i>	China	HKAS90958	OL860986	Liu et al. 2022a
<i>Hydnocristella himantia</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi48091	AJ292291	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>H. latihpha</i>	China	He20120911-3	KM489521	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>Kavinia alboviridis</i>	England	KM82737	GQ981505	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>K. chacoserrana</i> (T)	Argentina	Robledo2516	MF377531	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>Lentaria bambusina</i>	China	MHHNU7302	KU324496	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>L. byssisseda</i>	USA	TENN61159	FJ596785	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>L. patouillardii</i>	China	MHHNU7829	KU324498	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>L. surculus</i>	China	FHMU880	KU870451	Robledo & Urcelay 2017
<i>Phaeoclavulina abietina</i>	USA	OSC112178	KY510818	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. alboapiculata</i>	Italy	AMB18585	MT055964	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. arcosuensis</i>	Italy	AMB18532	MT055916	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. carovinacea</i>	Italy	AMB18534	MT055918	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. caroviridula</i>	Italy	AMB18536	MT055920	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. clavarioides</i>	Czech Republic	PRM945440	LR723646	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. cokeri</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi79893	MH322666	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. coniferarum</i>	Italy	AMB18562	MT055942	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. curta</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi48029	AJ408358	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. decurrens</i>	Portugal	MA-Fungi48019	MH322668	Martín et al. 2020
<i>P. flaccida</i>	Italy	AMB18544	MT055926	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. macrospora</i>	Italy	AMB18614	MT452510	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. minutispora</i>	Italy	AMB18588	MT055969	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. myceliosa</i>	USA	AGK035	JQ408230	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. nigricans</i>	Italy	AMB18589	MT055970	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. ochracea</i>	Italy	AMB18542	MT055924	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. quercus-ilicis</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi47984	AJ408382	Martín et al. 2020
<i>P. roellinii</i>	Czech Republic	PRM945446	LR723648	Liu et al. 2022b
<i>P. subdecurrens</i>	Spain	AH48370	MH322691	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria abetonensis</i> (T)	Italy	MCVE28638	KT357472	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria</i>	USA	WTU642	KY986439	Martín et al. 2020

<i>acriscescens</i>				
<i>Ramaria admiratia</i> (T)	USA	TENN69114	NR137862	Petersen et al. 2014
<i>Ramaria amyloidea</i>	USA	OSC66957	EU697258	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria apiculata</i>	Mexico	HC-PNNT179	KT307872	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria araiospora</i>	USA	OSC108301	EU852809	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria argentea</i>	USA	AGK042	JQ408234	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria aurantiiscescens</i>	USA	OSC73218	EU837198	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria aurea</i>	Germany	MA-Fungi48120	AJ408387	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria bataillei</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi48075	AF441082	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria beninensis</i> (T)	Benin	Christan1100	MH384904	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria botrytis</i> (T)	Italy	AMB18201	KY626151	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria calvodistalis</i> (T)	USA	TENN69095	NR137861	Petersen et al. 2014
<i>Ramaria cartilaginea</i>	USA	WTU43208	KY986436	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria celerivirescens</i>	USA	OSC140472	JX310385	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria comitis</i>	Portugal	AH48341	MH322667	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria conjuctipes</i>	USA	OSC81440	EU669377	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria coulterae</i> (T)	USA	TENN45771	KX574462	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria cyaneigranosa</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F043056	KX574465	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria cystidiophora</i>	Canada	UBC-F15182	DQ384590	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria fagetorum</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi48088	AJ408361	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria fennica</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi47996	AJ408352	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria fibulata</i> (T)	USA	TENN45709	KX574469	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria flava</i> (T)	Germany	ZT-Myc55613	KY626146	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria flavescens</i> (T)	Germany	TENN36864	KY626140	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria flavoides</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi47972	AJ408380	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria</i>	Switzerland	ZT-Myc54973	KY626135	Martín et al. 2020

<i>flavosalmonicolor</i> (T)				
<i>Ramaria formosa</i> (T)	Italy	AMB18199	KY626155	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria gelatiniaurantia</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F06304 9	KX574474	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria gracilis</i>	Mexico	unknown	EU258553	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria ignicolor</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi479 78	AJ408386	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria lacteobrunnescens</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi484 70	MH322682	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria largentii</i>	USA	OSC67012	KP658130	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria lorinthamnus</i>	New Zealand	PDD95771	HQ533039	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria maculatipes</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F06304 2	KX574476	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria magnifica</i> (T)	Italy	ZT-Myc57153	KY626136	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria mairei</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi398 78	AJ292296	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria obtusissima</i>	USA	TENN69158	KJ655554	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria pallidolilacina</i>	China	MHHNU7708	KU507207	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria pallidosaponaria</i> (T)	Italy	TENN36849	KY626142	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria parobotrytis</i> (T)	Italy	ZT-Myc-5893 0	MH216040	Direct submission by Franchi & Marchetti
<i>Ramaria praecox</i> (T)	Switzerland	ZT-Myc-Schil d2178	MF564297	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria pseudogracilis</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi480 67	AJ408384	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria rainierensis</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F06304 1	KX574466	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria rasilispora</i>	USA	S12B1601	KU574736	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria rubella</i>	USA	OSC140659	JX310405	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria rubiginosa</i>	USA	170-3	DQ365650	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria rubrievanescens</i>	USA	OSC134654	JX310408	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria rubripermanens</i>	USA	OSC70034	KY354754	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria</i>	USA	WTU-F06305	KX574484	Martín et al. 2020

<i>sandaracina</i> (T)		8		
<i>Ramaria sanguinea</i> (T)	Italy	AMB18200	KY626159	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria spinulosa</i>	Spain	MA-Fungi47990	AJ292293	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria stricta</i>	USA	OSC37039	KP658153	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria stuntzii</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F063050	KX574478	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria subtilis</i>	Spain	AH48020	MF564300	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria suecica</i>	USA	DG1218	KU574731	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria synaptopoda</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F063037	KX574485	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria testaceoflava</i>	USA	4441SL	KU574732	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria thiersii</i>	USA	OSC47006	KP658143	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria verlotensis</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F063047	KX574480	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Ramaria vinosimaculans</i> (T)	USA	WTU-F063043	KX574488	Martín et al. 2020
<i>Turbinellus floccosus</i>	USA	OSC66971	EU697242	Martín et al. 2020
<i>T. kauffmanii</i>	USA	iNat56243314	OK346519	Direct submission by Desanto et al.
“Uncultured fungus”	China	unknown	MF142383	Direct submission by Song & Chang; Du et al. 2019
Outgroup				
<i>Lysurus cruciatus</i>		MLHC-296	KY494890	Melanda et al. 2021
<i>Protuberia sabulonensis</i>	China	HKAS126430	OQ025166	Direct submission by Liu

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